

S1 Supplementary methods

Contents

S1 Supplementary methods.....	1
S1.1. Essential Variables for the Rights of Nature-Species (EVRoN-Species) methodology....	2
S1.1.1 Biospatial analysis (prediction of species)	3
S1.2 Community Engagement and Evidentiary Co-production	6
S1.3. Paraecologist field surveys	7
S1.3.1. Camera Trapping	7
S1.3.2 Sampling of small volant mammals (bats)	7
S1.3.3 Amphibian/Reptile Transects	8
S1.3.4 Biocultural value - study design and conceptual framework.....	8
S1.3.5. Ethnobotanical data collection.....	9
S1.3.6. Derivation of the Biocultural Value and Biocultural Score.....	9
S1.4 Essential Variables for the Rights of Nature-Community (EVRoN-Community) methodology	12
S1.4.1 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) aquatic macroinvertebrate sampling methodology	12
S1.4.2 Independent paraecologist/scientific team aquatic macroinvertebrate and water quality sampling methodology.....	14
S1.5 EVRoN-Ecosystem: Land-use, Forest Integrity and Spatial Analysis	17
S1.6 EVRoN-Biome Scale Terrain-Constrained Flow Path Modelling	18

This supplementary section details the methodological framework used to generate ecological evidence for the Essential Variables for the Rights of Nature (EVRoN), supporting the constitutional compatibility analysis presented in the main text. Methods are structured to align with the hierarchy of biological organisation and to produce evidence relevant to trigger, violation, and precautionary thresholds under Articles 71–74 of the Ecuadorian Constitution.

S1.1. Essential Variables for the Rights of Nature-Species (EVRoN-Species) methodology

Biospatial analysis was undertaken to generate a precautionary baseline of species presence/absence (EVRoN-Species) within the project area, constituting predicted evidence of ecological values relevant to constitutional thresholds. Global species distribution datasets obtained from the IUCN and BirdLife International were spatially clipped to the defined area of impact, producing a conservative estimate of species likely to occur within the concession.

An overview of the EVRoN-Species methodological workflow is presented in Figure S1.1.1. This integrates four components: (i) biospatial analysis, (ii) paraecologist field monitoring, (iii) collation of species-specific ecological characteristics, and (iv) Rights of Nature (RoN) Mapper analysis and indicator generation. Together, these steps produce a structured species evidence base for assessment under Articles 71–74, including identification of taxa requiring further population-level analysis to determine extinction risk.

Figure S1.1.1. Process diagram illustrating the generation of EVRoN-Species evidence (species presence/absence; EVRoN-SP) through the integration of biospatial modelling and paraecologist field surveys. Species predicted from IUCN and BirdLife distribution datasets were combined with field-confirmed observations to produce a precautionary species list for the concession area. This dataset was further enriched through integration of IUCN and national Red Lists, Evolutionarily Distinct and Globally Endangered (EDGE) species, and Key Biodiversity Area (KBA) indicator species, alongside literature-based identification of keystone and biocultural species. Species were mapped to constitutional Rights of Nature (RoN) Articles using the RoN-Mapper tool (REF), generating three indicators: Species per Article (SPA), Species Rights Risk Scores (SRRS), and the Evidence Completeness Index (ECI). Species activating one or more constitutional provisions are classified as Constitutionally Imperilled Species (CIS; predicted and field-confirmed) and Constitutionally Imperilled Ambassador Species (CIAS; field-confirmed). A subset of CIAS classified under IUCN threat categories (CR, EN, VU) are defined as Population-Risk CIAS (PR-

CIAS), requiring population-level assessment to evaluate extinction risk. These classifications provide structured inputs to Rights of Nature decision-making.

S1.1.1 Biospatial analysis (prediction of species)

Biospatial analyses were performed using ArcGIS Pro (version 3.1; ESRI, 2023) to generate a conservative estimate of species likely to occur within the project area. Global species range distribution polygons were obtained from the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and BirdLife International databases (Table S1.1.1) and spatially clipped to the defined area of impact for the Warintza concession (Fig. S1.1.2). Resulting attribute tables were used to compile a predicted species list representing EVRoN-Species baseline evidence.

Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) overlapping the project area were identified (Fig. S1.1.1), and associated KBA trigger species were incorporated into the dataset to capture species of recognised global conservation importance. Conservation status for all taxa was standardised using both IUCN Red List and national Red List classifications. Evolutionarily Distinct and Globally Endangered (EDGE) species were identified, and additional attributes including endemism, ecological function (e.g. keystone species), and conservation relevance were derived through targeted literature review.

Biocultural attributes were incorporated through comparison with documented plant and species use (e.g. *Enciclopedia de las plantas útiles del Ecuador*¹), applying the same classification protocol to biospatial species as used for EIA-derived records to ensure consistency. A further assessment of biocultural significance was undertaken to generate a biocultural score (see Section S1.3.5), contributing evidence relevant to Article 74 and to the identification of biocultural thresholds.

Interpretive function. The resulting dataset provides a precautionary evidentiary baseline for identifying EVRoN-Species trigger thresholds, including the presence of threatened, endemic, and evolutionarily distinct taxa, and supports the identification of plausible violation pathways associated with extinction risk.

Commented [MP1]: check

¹ Lucía de la Torre Navarrete, Hugo, Muriel M. ., Priscilla, Macía Barco, Manuel Juan, Balslev, Henrik (eds.), *Enciclopedia de Las Plantas Útiles Del Ecuador* (Quito : Herbario QCA de la Escuela de Ciencias Biológicas de la Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador ; Aarhus : Herbario AAU del Departamento de Ciencias Biológicas de la Universidad de Aarhus, 2008), <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/214428>.

Figure SI.1.2 Spatial extent of biospatial analysis for the Warintza project area. The hatched polygon represents the EIA study area, while the shaded polygon indicates the spatial extent used for EVRoN biospatial modelling. Mining concessions are shown by dashed boundaries, with the proposed mine footprint located centrally. The figure illustrates the conservative spatial delineation applied for species prediction relative to the formal EIA baseline. Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) overlapping the concession are also shown, including Territorios Shuar y Achuar (Tarimiat Pujutai Nunka y Kutuká–El Quimi–Cándor) and the adjacent Limón–Conchay–Agua Rica KBA.

Supplementary Table S1.1.1. Data sources for biospatial species modelling and conservation status classification.

Datasets	Sources	Notes
IUCN species distribution datasets	https://www.iucnredlist.org/resources/spatial-data-download	Anura, Caudata, Crayfish, Freshwater Crabs, Freshwater Fish, Freshwater Mammals, Freshwater Other, Freshwater Plants, Freshwater Shrimp, Gymnphiona, Marine & Terrestrial Mammals, Molluscs, Odonata, Plants, Reptiles, Terrestrial Mammals
BirdLife	https://datazone.birdlife.org/species/requestdis	Bird distribution datasets

National Red List Sources

Datasets	Sources	Notes
Ecuador National Red List for Amphibians	https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0251027	Published 2021
Ecuador National Red List for Fish	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/jfb.14844	Published 2021
Ecuador National Red List of Mammals	http://mesadeayuda.ambiente.gob.ec/Documentacion/Biodiversidad/pagina/listaRoja-Mamiferos.pdf	Published 2021
Ecuador National Red List of Plants	https://edipuce.edu.ec/libro-rojo-de-las-plantas-endemicas-del-ecuador/ León-Yáñez, S., R. Valencia, N. Pitman, L. Endara, C. Ulloa Ulloa & H. Navarrete (eds.). 2011. Libro rojo de las plantas endémicas del Ecuador, 2ª edición. Publicaciones del Herbario QCA, Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador, Quito.	Published 2012
Ecuador National Red list of Reptiles	https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/digital/56617.pdf	Published 2005
EDGE Species	https://www.edgeofexistence.org/explore-edge-species-country/	All EDGE Species

Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA) and KBA trigger species datasets

Datasets	Sources	Notes
Key Biodiversity Area Shapefiles	www.keybiodiversityareas.org	KBA Trigger Species Version Jan 2026 downloaded for Territorios Shuar y Achuar (Tarimiat Pujutai Nunka y Kutukú-El Quimi-Cóndor)

S1.2 Community Engagement and Evidentiary Co-production

Community engagement formed an integral component of the methodological design, enabling the co-production of ecological evidence through the systematic integration of Indigenous knowledge systems and independent scientific survey protocols. Ten Shuar paraecologists were selected by the Maikiuants local council (Shuar Territory) from within the Shuar Maikiuants community according to locally defined criteria of territorial knowledge, ecological expertise, and community representation. Participants undertook an intensive residential training programme between 22 April and 3 May 2024, delivered as part of a certified bespoke Continuing Education course entitled *Formación de Paraecólogos por los Derechos de la Naturaleza*. The curriculum combined theoretical and applied components, including: (i) standardised biodiversity monitoring techniques (e.g. line transect surveys, fixed-point observations, camera trapping, acoustic monitoring, and vegetation plot sampling), (ii) geospatial data collection using handheld GPS units and mobile data platforms, (iii) basic taxonomic identification across focal taxa (flora, avifauna, herpetofauna, and mammals), (iv) data recording, quality assurance and metadata standards, and (v) legal and conceptual frameworks underpinning the Rights of Nature in Ecuador.

Following training, paraecologists were embedded within interdisciplinary field teams comprising researchers and students from the University of Azuay. Paraecologists were responsible for primary data collection and site navigation, and data collation supported by scientific oversight to ensure protocol adherence and inter-observer reliability. Data were recorded using standardised datasheets and digital tools, enabling subsequent integration into a centralised database for validation and analysis.

This hybrid methodology ensured consistency and comparability of datasets through adherence to established ecological survey standards, while leveraging Indigenous ecological knowledge to optimise site selection, detect cryptic species, and interpret ecological patterns. Crucially, the approach expanded both the spatial and temporal coverage of sampling efforts, facilitating repeated observations, longitudinal tracking, and access to otherwise logistically challenging areas, thereby significantly exceeding the scope achievable through conventional Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) field surveys alone.

Data generated through this process include species observations, habitat characterisation, and biocultural knowledge, all of which are incorporated into the EVRoN evidence base. The inclusion of Indigenous knowledge enables identification of ecological relationships, species uses, and system dynamics that are not captured through desk-based or short-duration surveys, thereby contributing directly to evidentiary completeness within the EVRoN framework and supporting FPIC-consistent assessment processes (see Section 7.3.4 of the main text).

S1.3. Paraecologist field surveys

S1.3.1. Camera Trapping

Six camera trap stations were established to detect medium- and large-bodied terrestrial mammals, with placement guided by habitat features indicative of animal movement, including wildlife trails, ridge lines, and river margins. To avoid bias in the estimates of relative abundance and activity patterns, no attractants or baits were used. The cameras were distributed as follows: three units in the Yunkumas River micro-basin (two in the headwaters or upper zone, and one in the middle zone). To ensure the spatial independence of the recordings, a minimum separation distance of 1 km was maintained between consecutive devices (Table S1.3.1).

Table S1.3.1. Geographic coordinates, altitudes, and site codes of camera trap stations established across the Yunkumas and Aakas river micro-basins, showing spatial distribution of sampling locations.

Camera Code	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude
YK001	Yunkumas 3° 8'29.04"S	78°18'59.34"O	2095 m
YK002	Yunkumas 3° 8'15.61"S	78°18'32.16"O	1974 m
YK003	Yunkumas 3° 6'20.30"S	78°18'16.14"O	1172 m
YK004	Aakas 3° 06'26.7"S	78°15'59.7"O	1071 m
YK005	Aakas 3° 8'47.44"S	78°17'46.05"O	1513 m
YK006	Aakas 3° 9'0.57"S	78°18'5.90"O	1450m

After retrieving the data from camera traps, audiovisual records (photographs and videos) were analyzed to identify species occurring in each sub-basin. Taxonomic identification relied on specialized references, including the Updated Checklist of Mammals (2025), as well as the BioWeb, GBIF, and iNaturalist databases. Expert validation and the involvement of paraecologists from Maikiuants further supported the identification process. This collaborative effort resulted in a checklist of medium- and large-sized mammal species present in the territory of the Maikiuants community.

S1.3.2 Sampling of small volant mammals (bats)

This methodology describes a preliminary bat survey undertaken to develop an initial species inventory for the study area. Eight mist nets were deployed along a transect spanning agricultural areas, ecotonal zones, and piedmont forest, with a minimum spacing of 60m between nets. Nets were operated from 18:30 to 23:00 hours. Total effective sampling effort amounted to 36 net-hours, constrained by heavy rainfall. The survey was exploratory in nature, with particular emphasis on transitional habitats.

S1.3.3 Amphibian/Reptile Transects

Sampling was conducted in collaboration with paraecologists from the Maikiuants community. Five transects were established. In each transect, a technician and a community member conducted 3-hour nighttime surveys (19:00-22:00) using the Visual Encounter Survey (VES) methodology, which involves the active and systematic search for individuals in a defined area and time (Heyer et al., 2001). Exhaustive Search (ES) surveys were conducted for two-hour periods at varying times of day to detect species occupying cryptic or less accessible microhabitats.

This intensive sampling method records individuals in hard-to-reach microhabitats and is useful for rare or scarce species (INABIO, 2022).

Due to logistical limitations, sampling effort varied among transects. The total accumulated effort across the five transects using both methods is detailed in Table S1.3.3.

For each record, the following were noted: substrate, weather conditions, and individual activity. The captured juveniles and adults were transported individually in 8×12 cm transparent plastic bags with sufficient air and moist substrate to maintain humidity and appropriate temperature, and to prevent heat stress. The specimens were photographed and released back into their original habitat. Taxonomic identification was supported by expert consultation and by consulting the BioWeb Ecuador (www.bioweb.org) and AmphibiaWeb platforms. Unidentified species were designated “sp.”; related species or those belonging to species complexes were labeled “aff.” or “complex.” Finally, the threat category was assigned according to the IUCN Red List.

Table S1.3.2. Summary of amphibian and reptile transects conducted in the Maikiuants study area, including site codes, river systems, habitat type, geographic coordinates, and associated sampling effort (hours and distance surveyed).

Code	River	Habitat	Latitude	Longitude	Hours	Kilometers
TA1	Aakas	Río y Bosque	-3.120882	-78.270678	16	11.90
TA2	Aakas	Río y Bosque	-3.114250	-78.259983	2	6.47
TA3	Aakas	Río y Bosque	-3.102245	-78.299442	3	3.25
TY1	Yunkumas	Río y Bosque	-3.098245	-78.295890	8	7.66
TY2	Yunkumas	Río y Bosque	-3.09722	-78.295067	5	6.13

S1.3.4 Biocultural value - study design and conceptual framework

A mixed-methods ethnobotanical approach² was applied to document biocultural relationships between the Shuar Maikiuants community and plant species. The design integrates qualitative and quantitative methods, combining documentation of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) with

² Sawko, A (2025). “[Recentering Indigenous Rights and Knowledge to Protect Shuar Territory: Ethnobotany, Biocultural Mapping, and the Rights of Nature in the Ecuadorian Amazon](#)”. MSc thesis for Global Biodiversity Conservation MSc 2024-2025, University of Sussex, UK.

structured ecological sampling. Methods were adapted from established ethnobotanical protocols and aligned to enable integration with EIA-derived datasets³⁴⁵.

Study area: Fieldwork was conducted between June and July 2025 in the Maikiuants territory, Cordillera del Cndor, Morona Santiago, Ecuador. The study area (~850 m elevation) includes primary forest, secondary forest, and finca systems forming a heterogeneous landscape mosaic.

Ethical considerations and Indigenous knowledge protection: Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Sussex, University of Azuay, and the Royal Geographical Society. Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC) was obtained, with verbal consent recorded. Participants were anonymised, and sensitive data stored securely. Voucher collection occurred with community approval and specimens were deposited at the University of Azuay Herbarium.

Commented [MP2]: NEED TO ADD MINISTRY COLLECTION PERMIT

S1.3.5. Ethnobotanical data collection

Semi-structured interviews: Eight semi-structured interviews were conducted following ethnobotanical best practices⁶⁷. Interviews were recorded, transcribed, translated, and coded in NVivo 14 using an iterative thematic framework and species lists generated.

Free-listing and plant walks: Fourteen informants participated in free-listing and guided plant walks. For each plant, local name, scientific identification, use categories, plant parts, and GPS coordinates were recorded. Taxonomy was standardised using GBIF and conservation status cross-checked with IUCN.

Ecological sampling: belt transects: Vegetation surveys followed adapted belt transect methodology⁸. Nine transects (50 × 5 m) were established across habitats (primary, secondary, finca) with ethnobotanically used species only recorded within transects.

S1.3.6. Derivation of the Biocultural Value and Biocultural Score

A biocultural value classification was developed to identify species evidencing documented relationships with human use, cultural practice, or ecological knowledge. This classification was applied consistently across biospatial, EIA-derived, and field-verified datasets to ensure comparability. A binary indicator (presence/absence of biocultural relevance) was used within the RoN Mapper, while a continuous Biocultural Score was derived to enable prioritisation for further analysis.

³ Martin, G.J. (2010). *Ethnobotany: A Methods Manual*. Routledge.

⁴ Phillips, O.L. et al. (2003). "Efficient plot-based floristic assessment of tropical forests." *Journal of Tropical Ecology*, 19, 629–645.

⁵ Silva, H.C.H. et al. (2014). "Evaluating methods used in ethnobotanical and ecological studies to record plant biodiversity." *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 10, 48.

⁶ Giday, M., Asfaw, Z., & Woldu, Z. (2009). "Medicinal plants of the Meinit ethnic group: an ethnobotanical study." *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 124, 513–521.

⁷ Martin, G.J. (2010). *Ethnobotany: A Methods Manual*. Routledge.

⁸ Martin, G.J. (2010). *Ethnobotany: A Methods Manual*. Routledge.

Biocultural Score is a more nuanced analysis and assigned as follows. The EIA identified plant use by comparison against the Enciclopedia de las plantas útiles del Ecuador⁹. For species identified in our biospatial analysis the same protocol was applied. Biocultural score was operationalised as an ordinal measure of culturally embedded human-plant relationships, designed to ensure comparability between field-verified data and desk-based EIA sources. Only categories evidencing direct human-plant interactions (Table 1.3.3) were included in the assessment. Ecological descriptors lacking explicit human interaction (e.g. trophic roles) were excluded from biocultural scoring but are treated separately as a proxy value for community-level knowledge of ecosystems.

Each eligible use category was assigned a relational depth weight a priori (high = 1.0; medium = 0.7; low = 0.4), reflecting the degree to which the category typically indicates culturally embedded and knowledge-intensive relationships rather than incidental use (Table 1.3.3.). For each species, a cumulative relationship strength score (S) was calculated as the sum of relational weights across all documented categories. Species were then assigned to one of three biocultural tiers using fixed thresholds: none (S = 0), documented (0 < S < 1.4), or strong (S ≥ 1.4), with strong designation requiring multi-dimensional evidence of relational engagement. To account for epistemic differences between datasets, biocultural tiers were adjusted using a binary confidence multiplier distinguishing field-verified community knowledge (multiplier = 1.0) from literature-based evidence (multiplier = 0.5). The final Biocultural Score was calculated as: Biocultural Score = Tier × Confidence multiplier. This approach provides a transparent and replicable proxy for relational depth where informant-level ethnobotanical indices (e.g. Cultural Importance Index or Use Value) cannot be computed across all datasets. By separating relationship depth from evidence confidence, the method preserves comparability, avoids conflation of ecological traits with cultural relationships, and makes uncertainty explicit in Rights of Nature-oriented environmental assessment.

Table 1.3.3. Weights applied to species identified as having biocultural value. In this analysis, a value of 0 was assigned to the ecological category, as this dimension is more closely associated with understanding the ecological system and is therefore analysed separately.

S (Category)	T (Weight)	Source
Behavioural	1	Sawko ¹⁰
Construction	0.7	Sawko

⁹ Lucía de la Torre Navarrete, Hugo, Muriel M., Priscilla, Macía Barco, Manuel Juan, Balslev, Henrik (eds.), *Enciclopedia de Las Plantas Útiles Del Ecuador* (Quito : Herbario QCA de la Escuela de Ciencias Biológicas de la Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador ; Aarhus : Herbario AAU del Departamento de Ciencias Biológicas de la Universidad de Aarhus, 2008), <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/214428>; William J. Ripple et al., ‘Status and Ecological Effects of the World’s Largest Carnivores’, *Science* 343, no. 6167 (2014): 1241484, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1241484>.

¹⁰ Sawko, A (2025). *“Recentering Indigenous Rights and Knowledge to Protect Shuar Territory: Ethnobotany, Biocultural Mapping, and the Rights of Nature in the Ecuadorian Amazon”*. MSc thesis for Global Biodiversity Conservation MSc 2024-2025, University of Sussex, UK.

Cosmetic	0.4	Sawko
Craft	1	Sawko
Ecological	0	Sawko
Environmental	0.7	EIA ¹¹
Food	0.7	Sawko
Fuel	0.4	Sawko
Hunting	0.7	Sawko
Hygiene	0.4	Sawko
Indicator	1	Sawko
Materials	0.7	EIA
Medicinal	0.7	Sawko
Ritual	1	Sawko
Sacred	1	Sawko
Social	1	EIA
Veterinary	0.7	Sawko

The interpretation of the final values is defined across a range from 0 to 1. A score of 0 indicates no documented biocultural relevance, while a score of 0.25 reflects low significance and/or low confidence. A value of 0.5 represents moderate significance or reduced evidentiary confidence, and a score of 1 denotes high biocultural significance supported by strong evidence.

The calculation proceeds in three steps. First, a weighted intensity score (S) is computed as the sum of all documented uses multiplied by their assigned weights. Second, this value is converted into a categorical significance tier based on predefined thresholds. Third, the result is adjusted by a confidence factor reflecting the evidentiary source (field-verified or literature-based). The final Biocultural Score is therefore expressed as:

$$BC_i = f(\sum(U_{i,c} \times W_c)) \times Conf_i$$

where:

BC_i = final biocultural score for species i

$U_{i,c}$ = presence or extent of use of species i in category c

W_c = weight assigned to use category c

¹¹ Lowell Mineral Exploration Ecuador S.A., *Estudio de Impacto Ambiental y Plan de Manejo Ambiental Para Las Fases de Explotación y Beneficio Del Área Operativa Del Proyecto Minero Warintza, Así Como Infraestructura Complementaria En Ella.*

$\sum(U_{i,c} \cdot W_c)$ = weighted sum of all recorded uses (intensity, S)

$f(\cdot)$ = function that converts intensity into a categorical significance tier

$Conf_i$ = confidence factor reflecting evidentiary strength for species i

The resulting score is bounded between 0 and 1, ensuring compatibility with EVRoN model inputs, where all criteria are normalised to a common scale. This normalisation prevents biocultural variables from exerting disproportionate influence on outcomes while still maintaining sensitivity to cultural embeddedness, relational value, and knowledge provenance.

Methodologically, this formulation is intentionally conservative in two ways. First, threshold compression ensures that high-intensity biocultural relationships, such as those involving multiple uses, are capped at a maximum tier value of 1. Second, confidence scaling reduces the weighting of non-fieldwork evidence, which may lead to underrepresentation of documented but indirect knowledge. As a result, the scoring system prioritises species that are strongly supported by evidence and are relationally significant, rather than maximising differentiation across all possible uses. The resulting list of species is ranked, with those identified as at risk of extinction flagged for population-level analysis. Species recognised as playing key ecological roles, based on fieldwork or literature, are also highlighted as providing a proxy for ecological knowledge.

S1.4 Essential Variables for the Rights of Nature-Community (EVRoN-Community) methodology

S1.4.1 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) aquatic macroinvertebrate sampling methodology

The EIA Sampling design is detailed in the EIA¹², with an overview here. Aquatic macroinvertebrates were sampled at 14 sites (labelled MCR-01 to MCR-14) located in rivers and streams within the Warintza project area (Morona Santiago, Ecuador) during April–May 2024. Sampling sites encompassed lotic systems with variable habitat conditions, including differences in channel width (0.1–20 m), depth (0.05–1.7 m), substrate composition (rocky, sandy, and clay), flow regimes, and riparian vegetation cover. A quantitative standardised protocol was applied at all sites to ensure comparability. Each sampling reach covered approximately 100 m with 10 Sub-samples of 1 minute were taken aiming to cover representative local habitat.

Field sampling procedure: Macroinvertebrates were collected using a D-frame kick sampling net. At each site (seven), sampling targeted a range of microhabitats to capture community heterogeneity, including: rocky substrates and sediments, submerged vegetation and woody debris, leaf litter accumulations, water column and margins. Sampling consisted of systematic multi-

¹² Lowell Mineral Exploration Ecuador S.A., *Estudio de Impacto Ambiental y Plan de Manejo Ambiental Para Las Fases de Explotación y Beneficio Del Área Operativa Del Proyecto Minero Warintza, Así Como Infraestructura Complementaria En Ella*. Pages 627-639

habitat sweeps, typically covering 10 microhabitats per site, with approximately 1 minute of active sampling per microhabitat. Collected organisms were preserved in 75% ethanol, labeled *in situ*, and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

Laboratory processing and taxonomic identification: Samples were sorted under a stereomicroscope and identified to the lowest feasible taxonomic level (family, genus, and morphospecies) using regional taxonomic keys and reference literature (e.g., Roldán, Domínguez & Fernández, Merritt & Cummins). Individuals were counted to obtain abundance data for each morphospecies. Identified specimens were curated and stored in a reference collection.

Community metrics and diversity analysis: Basic ecological metrics were calculated, including: Taxonomic richness (S), Total abundance (N), Relative abundance, Diversity indices (Shannon–Wiener H', Simpson 1–D), Equitability (J), Chao 1 estimator for sampling completeness, Similarity indices (e.g., Jaccard) with analyses performed using statistical software (Past v4.12, Excel).

BMWP/Col index: Water quality was assessed using the BMWP/Col (Biological Monitoring Working Party – Colombian adaptation¹³) index. This index is based on the presence of macroinvertebrate families and their assigned tolerance scores (1–10), reflecting sensitivity to organic pollution. The BMWP/Col score for each site was calculated as the sum of tolerance values of all recorded families. Water quality classes were defined as follows: >150: Very good / clean waters, 101–120: Good quality, 61–100: Acceptable, 36–60: Doubtful, 16–35: Critical, <15: Very critical

AAMBI index: The Andean–Amazon Biotic Index¹⁴ (AAMBI) was applied to evaluate ecological integrity. Similar to BMWP/Col, this index uses family-level scores (1–10) reflecting sensitivity to environmental disturbance. The AAMBI score was calculated as the sum of family scores per site, and classified as: >121: Excellent, 90–120: Very good, 50–89: Good, 36–49: Fair

¹³ The Biological Monitoring Working Party index adapted for Colombia (BMWP/Col) is a macroinvertebrate-based biotic scoring system derived from the original BMWP framework, in which aquatic invertebrate families are assigned scores according to their tolerance to organic pollution. The index has been widely adapted for tropical Andean systems to account for regional ecological conditions and taxonomic assemblages, and is commonly applied as an indicator of ecological status and water quality in Colombia and across Latin America (i.e. Roldán-Pérez, G., 'Macroinvertebrates as bioindicators of water quality: four decades of development in Colombia and Latin America' (2016) 40(155) *Revista de la Academia Colombiana de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales* 254).

¹⁴ The Andean-Amazon Biotic Index (AAMBI) is a macroinvertebrate-based biotic scoring system developed for tropical Andean and Amazonian freshwater ecosystems, in which aquatic invertebrate families are assigned tolerance scores reflecting their sensitivity to organic pollution and environmental disturbance. The index builds on established Andean biotic frameworks by incorporating regionally calibrated tolerance values suited to high-altitude tropical catchments and Amazonian foothill systems, and is applied as an indicator of ecological condition and water quality in integrated bioassessment studies across the Andean–Amazon region (i.e. Cabrera-García, S. et al., 'Taxonomic and Feeding Trait-Based Analysis of Macroinvertebrates in the Antisana River Basin (Ecuadorian Andean Region)' (2023) 12(11) *Biology* 1386)

<35, Poor. This index is particularly suitable for regional bioassessment due to its calibration for Andean and Amazonian river systems.

EPT index: The EPT index¹⁵ was calculated as the percentage of individuals belonging to the orders Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera, and Trichoptera, which are sensitive to pollution.

EPT (%)=number of EPT individuals/total individuals. Water quality was interpreted as: 75–100%: Very good, 50–74%: Good, 25–49%: Fair, 0–24%: Poor

Ecological interpretation: Macroinvertebrates were used as bioindicators of water quality and ecosystem integrity due to their: high taxonomic diversity, varying tolerance to pollution relatively sedentary nature, extended aquatic life cycles. Additional ecological attributes evaluated included trophic guilds, habitat preference (benthic, neustonic, nectonic), and sensitivity classes, supporting interpretation of environmental conditions and anthropogenic impacts.

S1.4.2 Independent paraecologist/scientific team aquatic macroinvertebrate and water quality sampling methodology

Aquatic ecosystem assessments were conducted at eight sampling stations located within the Aakas, Yunkumas, and Coangos river systems. Macroinvertebrate and water sampling, as well as *in-situ* physicochemical measurements, were carried out during September 2024 and February 2025. Additional water samples from the Coangos River were collected in April 2026. Due to its large size, macroinvertebrate sampling and flow measurements were not conducted in the Coangos River, where only water quality analyses were performed.

Sampling sites (AE1–AE3, YE1–YE4, and CO1, Table S2.2.1) were distributed along upper, middle, and lower sections of each system, encompassing variation in altitude, hydrological conditions, and anthropogenic influence.

¹⁵ The Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Trichoptera (EPT) index is a macroinvertebrate-based metric in which the richness or relative abundance of taxa belonging to these pollution-sensitive orders is used as an indicator of ecological condition, with higher EPT values reflecting better water quality and lower levels of anthropogenic disturbance; the approach is grounded in the recognised sensitivity of these taxa to environmental stressors and has been widely applied in river biomonitoring and ecological assessment (i.e. Vimos-Lojano, D.J. et al., 'Riparian and microhabitat factors determine the structure of the EPT community in Andean headwater rivers of Ecuador' (2017) 10(8) Ecohydrology.)

Sampling locations: Sampling was conducted at the sites shown in Table S2.4.1.

Table S2.4.1. Sampling locations for aquatic macroinvertebrate communities, riverine structure and water quality in our independent surveys

River	Station Code	Latitude	Longitude	Section
Aakas River	AE1	3.152310	-78.295477	Upper
Aakas River	AE2	3.152692	-78.294121	Middle
Aakas River	AE3	3.147898	-78.284422	Lower
Yunkumas River	YE1	3.133726	-78.319858	Upper
Yunkumas River	YE2	3.104302	-78.303282	Middle
Yunkumas River	YE3	3.104273	-78.303265	Middle
Yunkumas River	YE4	3.100197	-78.298008	Lower
Coangos River	CO1	3.111760	-78.215630	Lower

Physicochemical and habitat variables: Riparian and fluvial habitat conditions were assessed using two standardised indices. The Riparian Forest Quality Index¹⁶ (QBR) was applied to evaluate riparian vegetation cover, structure, ecological quality, and degree of alteration of the river corridor. The Fluvial Habitat Index¹⁷ (FHI) was used to characterize channel physical conditions, including substrate heterogeneity, channel morphology, and habitat features relevant to benthic fauna. Interpretation thresholds followed established criteria, where QBR values ≥ 96 indicate pristine riparian conditions and ≤ 50 indicate severe degradation. For FHI, values ≥ 75 represent optimal habitat quality, while values ≤ 40 indicate poor conditions for aquatic macroinvertebrates.

¹⁶ The Riparian Forest Quality Index (QBR; *Qualitat del Bosc de Ribera*) is a field-based index designed to assess the ecological condition of riparian vegetation through four components: total riparian cover, vegetation structure, cover quality (including native species and disturbance), and channel alteration, producing a score ranging from 0 (highly degraded) to 100 (natural condition). Originally developed for Mediterranean rivers, the QBR has been widely adapted and applied in tropical regions of Latin America, including studies in Mexico and other Neotropical systems, demonstrating its usefulness for evaluating riparian forest integrity and its relationship with vegetation structure and diversity.

¹⁷ The Fluvial Habitat Index (FHI) is an integrated measure of physical habitat quality in river systems, incorporating channel morphology, substrate composition, flow characteristics, and habitat heterogeneity. It is commonly used as an environmental gradient to interpret biological responses, particularly of benthic macroinvertebrate communities, in freshwater biomonitoring studies. Applications in tropical South American river basins (e.g. Ecuador and Panama) have shown that FHI scores are sensitive to anthropogenic disturbance, with higher values associated with less impacted, structurally diverse habitats and better ecological condition

In-situ physicochemical measurements: At each sampling station, physicochemical parameters were measured using calibrated submersible probes. Dissolved oxygen and temperature were measured using a YSI ProODO meter, while pH, electrical conductivity, and total dissolved solids were recorded using a HANNA HI 991300 device. Hydromorphological conditions were characterized by measuring flow velocity with a digital current meter (Global Water FP111, Xylem, USA). Channel width and depth were measured along transects to calculate discharge using the velocity–area method. Water samples were also collected at each site, stored at 4°C, and transported to the laboratory for subsequent chemical analysis of nutrients, major ions, and trace metals.

Field sampling procedure, Macroinvertebrates: At each river station, a 50m reach was established for biological sampling. Within each reach, three subsampling points were selected to represent the diversity of available habitats, with preference given to riffle zones due to their higher biodiversity. Macroinvertebrates were collected using a D-frame kick net. Sampling consisted of three integrated subsamples, each with approximately one minute of active sampling effort, covering microhabitats such as coarse substrates, sediments, leaf litter, and submerged vegetation. Collected organisms were preserved in situ in 96% ethanol and labelled for laboratory processing.

Laboratory processing and taxonomic identification: Samples were sorted and identified under a Leica EZ4HD stereomicroscope. Macroinvertebrates were identified to the lowest feasible taxonomic level using regional taxonomic keys and reference literature (e.g., Domínguez & Fernández, Rincón et al.). Specimens were counted to obtain abundance data and preserved as part of a reference collection.

Community metrics and ecological indices: To assess ecological integrity, two primary biotic indices were applied: AAMBI (Andean–Amazon Biotic Index): calculated and classified as in the EIA described above (Section 1.4.1), EPT Index: calculated and classified as in the EIA described above.

Laboratory analysis of water samples: Water samples collected in the field were analysed in the laboratory for dissolved ions and trace metals. Major anions, including fluoride (F^-), chloride (Cl^-), nitrite (NO_2^-), bromide (Br^-), nitrate (NO_3^-), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), and sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), were measured using a Thermo Dionex ICS-1600 ion chromatograph. Trace metals, including lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), copper (Cu), and zinc (Zn), were quantified using a Thermo iCE-3000 atomic absorption spectrometer.

Ecological interpretation: Aquatic macroinvertebrates and physicochemical parameters were used jointly to evaluate water quality, habitat condition, and ecosystem integrity. Macroinvertebrates serve as reliable bioindicators due to their sensitivity to environmental changes, diverse ecological roles, limited mobility, and relatively long aquatic life cycles. The integration of biological indices, structural habitat quality metrics (QBR and FHI), physicochemical measurements, and laboratory-based water chemistry analyses allows for a

comprehensive assessment of river ecosystem health and the identification of potential anthropogenic impacts.

S1.5 EVRoN-Ecosystem: Land-use, Forest Integrity and Spatial Analysis

The EVRoN-Ecosystem component was designed to generate spatially explicit evidence of ecosystem condition, integrity, and land-use structure within the study area, contributing to assessment under Articles 71 and 72 of the Ecuadorian Constitution. The analysis focuses on forest cover, land-use dynamics, and fragmentation as indicators of ecosystem function, resilience, and restoration potential.

Spatial datasets and preprocessing: Spatial analysis was conducted using QGIS (version 3.x), integrating satellite imagery, territorial planning data, and national land-use classification frameworks. The primary dataset consisted of high-resolution satellite imagery (3 m spatial resolution) acquired on 7 August 2025. Imagery was pre-processed to ensure radiometric consistency and clipped to the defined study extent corresponding to the Maikiuants territory and surrounding concession area. Additional spatial layers included: Indigenous territorial zoning derived from the Shuar Arutam Plan de Vida (2016–2026), National land-use classification datasets (MAE–MAGAP 2023) and Project infrastructure layers (mine footprint, roads, concessions). All spatial data were projected to a common coordinate system (WGS84 / UTM Zone 17S) and aligned using a consistent grid, extent, and resolution to ensure comparability across analyses.

Land-use classification: Land use was classified using a combined supervised and unsupervised remote sensing approach to ensure both replicability and sensitivity to local ecological variation.

Unsupervised classification: An initial unsupervised classification was performed using a K-means clustering algorithm, generating 15 spectral classes based on pixel reflectance values across RGB bands. This step provided an initial grouping of land-cover types without pre-defined training data and enabled identification of spatially coherent landscape units across the study area.

Supervised classification: A supervised classification was subsequently applied using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier. Training data were derived from; field observations, paraecologist knowledge, visually interpreted satellite imagery, high-resolution orthophotos generated from UAV surveys.

Training polygons were assigned to land-use classes based on ecological and management categories. The classifier was then applied to the full image dataset to produce the final land-use map.

UAV surveys and orthophoto integration: Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) surveys were conducted to generate high-resolution orthophotos for selected areas within the study site. Drone imagery was processed to produce orthomosaics using standard photogrammetric workflows.

Orthophotos were used to validate land-use classification outputs, identify fine-scale landscape features not detectable in satellite imagery, generate and refine training data for supervised classification, support field verification of land-use categories. The integration of UAV-derived data improved classification accuracy, particularly in areas where canopy heterogeneity, shadowing, or mixed land-use reduced the discriminative capacity of satellite imagery alone.

Land-use categories: Final classifications were aggregated into four functional land-use types; Strict conservation: areas with minimal disturbance and high ecological integrity (primary forest), Low-use forest: areas with limited subsistence use and low-intensity disturbance, Sustainable use: agroforestry systems, secondary forests, and managed landscapes, Infrastructure and degraded areas: roads, settlements, mining areas, and other high-impact land uses

Area calculation and spatial metrics: For each land-use class, total area (hectares) and proportional coverage (%) were calculated relative to the total study area.

Integration with Indigenous territorial planning: Land-use classification was interpreted in the context of Indigenous territorial governance by integrating zoning categories from the Shuar Arutam Plan de Vida. These categories define intended land-use functions, including conservation areas, subsistence use zones, and areas designated for community development. Spatial comparison between observed land-use patterns and planned territorial zoning was conducted to assess; consistency between current land use and Indigenous governance frameworks, potential areas of conflict or mismatch with proposed mining activities

S1.6 EVRoN-Biome Scale Terrain-Constrained Flow Path Modelling

Flow-Path and Downstream Exposure Analysis: A terrain-constrained, catchment-scale flow-routing and geomorphic screening analysis was conducted to delineate conservative downstream exposure envelopes under a hypothetical tailings dam failure scenario.

The analysis is explicitly screening-level and does not simulate breach mechanics, flow velocities, or inundation depths. Instead, it identifies areas that cannot reasonably be excluded from potential impact based on gravitational and geomorphic connectivity, consistent with precautionary EIA practice. The approach assumes gravity-driven transport along topographically defined pathways, without attenuation or engineered containment, and is therefore intentionally conservative in defining potential exposure. Spatial analyses were conducted using ArcGIS Pro (Esri, Redlands, CA, USA).

Digital Elevation Model Datasets: The primary terrain dataset was the Copernicus GLO-30 Digital Elevation Model (30 m resolution) obtained via OpenTopography (<https://opentopography.org>). This resolution is appropriate for catchment-scale connectivity analysis, providing hydrological stability while avoiding artefacts associated with finer-resolution DEMs in steep, forested terrain.

GIS processing and flow-path derivation: The DEM was projected from GCS WGS 1984 to WGS 84 / UTM Zone 17S to ensure metric consistency. Pre-processing steps included sink filling to enforce hydrological continuity and the generation of all derivative rasters within a standardised processing environment (consistent cell size, snap raster, and spatial extent).

Hydrological analysis was performed using standard GIS tools:

- Flow direction was calculated using the D8 algorithm to define downslope pathways
- Flow accumulation was derived to identify drainage networks
- A DEM-derived downstream flow path was generated from the assumed tailings dam outlet to the basin outlet, representing directional hydrological connectivity

Geomorphic screening and impact delineation: Potentially impactable terrain was delineated using a DEM-based geomorphic screening approach. Grid cells were classified as susceptible where both of the following conditions were met; flow-connected distance to drainage ≤ 1000 m and local slope $\leq 5\%$. These criteria identify low-gradient valley floor and floodplain environments where deposition, spreading, or ponding of tailings material is plausible. The thresholds were selected as conservative approximations of reduced energy environments in which transported material is likely to accumulate.

Connectivity modelling and validation: Spatial connectivity was enforced using a cost-distance propagation approach, with the derived downstream flow path used as the source feature. This method enables lateral propagation of potential exposure across valley-confined terrain while preventing unrealistic cross-ridge or upslope spread. Model outputs were visually validated against hillshade representations and valley morphology, cross-checked for consistency with drainage network structure and clipped to the defined analysis domain.

Ancillary spatial datasets included:

Protected Areas (UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, 2026; <https://www.protectedplanet.net>)

Indigenous territories (ICCA Registry; <https://www.iccaregistry.org>)

National cartography (IGM Ecuador; <https://www.geoportaligm.gob.ec/portal/>)